

COPOLYAMIDE NANOCOMPOSITES BY CAST AND FILM BLOWING PROCESSES

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SUMMARY

Hybrids based on a commercial copolyamide and containing different silicate amounts were initially produced by melt compounding and then submitted to cast and blowing film extrusions. Oxygen permeability and tensile mechanical results were correlated to nanomorphology and crystal structure through rheological, TEM and DSC analyses.

Keywords: copolyamide nanocomposites, cast film, blowing, permeability, morphology.

INTRODUCTION

Cast and blowing film extrusions are very common techniques for producing polyamides within packaging industry. A recent strategy to improve polyamide performances and extend their application fields is offered by the reinforcement with nanometric layered silicates but the difficulty in controlling nanostructure hinders their production on industrial scale [1]. It is well known that type and entity of flow field involved during manufacturing processes strongly affects structure, properties and processability. In particular, elongational flow plays a key role during film processes and the desired performances of polyamide nanocomposite films could be optimized by opportunely controlling the orientation along one or two directions. However, the works in literature on film production of polyamide nanocomposites are still very few and the analysis of final nanostructure becomes complex due to the semi-crystalline nature of polyamides.

In the present work, cast and blowing film processes of polyamide based nanocomposites were analyzed. Hybrids at different silicate amounts were initially produced by melt compounding using a commercial copolyamide and then submitted to cast and blowing film extrusions. Oxygen permeability and tensile mechanical results were correlated to nanomorphology and crystal structure through rheological, TEM and DSC analyses.

EXPERIMENTAL

Raw materials used were organically modified montmorillonite (Cloisite 30B by Southern Clay Product) and a commercial copolymer of nylon 6. Nanocomposites at 3 and 6wt% of silicate were prepared by melt compounding with a twin screw extruder at 100 rpm imposing a temperature profile of 260-255-250-245°C. Film casting was

realized with a single screw extruder (Gimac, L/D=24) having a rectangular 0.25 X 200 mm² die. A chill roll rate of 10 m/min was used to collect the films. Blown films were obtained using a Brabender DCE 330 single-screw extruder (L=400mm; L/D= 20), equipped with an annular die (30 and 32mm inner and outer diameters). The films were collected with BUR=2.5 and DR=23.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Nanostructural modifications induced by uniaxial elongational flow were investigated by means rheological analyses performed with an extensional rheometer (SER). Despite neat matrix, nanocomposite samples showed a peculiar strain hardening behavior of extensional viscosity which was related to a silicate three-dimensional arrangement promoted by stretching. [2]. Fiber spinning tests were also carried out in order to better understand the potential stretchability of nanocomposites. The results demonstrated that the presence of silicate inside copolyamide matrix led to increased draw-down force, while the breaking draw ratio decreases, as result of the reinforcement from the nanolayered silicate. Moreover bubble stability of nanocomposites resulted good at low silicate loading.

In Table 1 oxygen permeability data related to cast and blown nanocomposite films at different silicate amounts are reported.

Table 1 – Permeability data of cast and blown nanocomposite films.

sample	Cast Films		Blown Films	
	P cm ³ cm/m ² dbar	% increment O ₂ barrier	P cm ³ cm/m ² dbar	% increment O ₂ barrier
matrix	0.207	-	0.174	-
+3%	0.138	34	0.122	30
+6%	0.095	54	0.114	35

In both film types, the presence of silicate inside polymer matrix leads to oxygen permeability reduction suggesting reasonable degree of exfoliation which makes more tortuous the diffusive path of the gas through the polymer [3]. By comparing the properties of the two kind of films, it can be observed that films obtained by cast film process exhibit higher gas barrier enhancements when compared to the corresponding hybrids by film blowing. Such differences, also pointed out from mechanical analyses, can be attributed to different silicate arrangement (in terms of exfoliation and orientation) and crystal structures induced within the two film processes, as confirmed by morphological and thermal characterization.

References

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